

THE STRANGE PULSE TOOLKIT

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ABSTRACT

The Strange Pulse Toolkit¹ is a collection of modular components, utilities, and examples written for the Max platform². It is designed to facilitate the use of strange attractors in experimental musical practice. Its purpose is to encourage the creation of instruments that emphasise the non-linear and unpredictable nature of strange attractors, embracing the concept of co-creation that requires ceding control back into instrument itself. The toolkit draws on experimental, cybernetic and material oriented perspectives of instrument design. It offers a unique set of tools along with examples and utilities that encourage unpredictability, exploration and unmastery as guiding principles. The musical context for the toolkit is discussed, followed by an explanation of the toolkit itself. An in-depth personal case study is presented, looking at the way in which the toolkit was developed as part of an artistic practice.

1. INTRODUCTION

Adding non-linear and chaotic dynamics into software instruments might seem counter intuitive. A lot of traditional discourse around musical practice highlights *mastery* and *control* as fundamental skills through which you can realise musical ideas [1]. Intentionally adding unpredictable and uncontrollable characteristics to an instrument is clearly in conflict with those skills.

1.1 Materiality

However, there are some perspectives within experimental musical practice that take a *co-creative* stance, that utilise the idiosyncrasies of an instrument (), within their creative process. The instrument is seen as a source of creativity, rather than simply a conduit through which creative ideas flow.

Mudd [2] calls these two perspectives communication-oriented and material-oriented. A communication-oriented stance is concerned with transmitting pre-conceived ideas from the composers mind and trying to realise those ideas with as little loss or distortion as possible. There is an

¹ <https://github.com/MaxWorgan/StrangePulseToolkit>

² <https://cyclling74.com/products/max>

implication with this perspective that the tools used (i.e. the instrument) should be as transparent and controllable as possible.

A material-oriented perspective on the other hand, proposes that creative ideas are developed through exploration with tools and their specific properties. In this view, the instrument is not just a passive conduit but an active participant in the creative process. The unique characteristics and behaviors of the instrument can be the source of creative ideas, rather than flaws to avoid.

1.2 Non-Linear Instruments

Instruments that foreground some kind of non-linearity in their designs are particularly well placed to confront this question of materiality vs communicative perspective. Acoustic instruments all contain non-linearities in the way they function, reed and wind instruments are often cited as clear and obvious examples. These characteristics are well known and well studied [3]. The material characteristics of the physical instrument combine with the constraints of our bodies, mediated via the laws of thermodynamics to create an interaction that is highly non-linear, at times unpredictable, and often beguiling. Magnusson [4] argues that these complexities of interaction might be linked to the long term appeal of acoustic instruments.

There is a burgeoning interest in digital or part digital instruments that have deliberately chosen some non-linear mechanism to be an integral aspect of their interface. This includes, but is not limited to, instruments involving feedback, whether built around a physical interface [5], no input mixers [6,7], or chaotic systems [2]. The unpredictable nature of such systems, rather than being seen as a hindrance, can be viewed as a rich source of creative potential. But in embracing the unpredictable and often surprising nature of such instruments, it is not just questions of control and mastery that need to be considered, but also those of agency and authorship.

1.3 Unmastery

Melbye's [8] concept of 'Unmastery' is relevant here, which rejects the ideas of mastery, control and virtuosity and instead embraces the *resistances* that an instrument offers. These resistances can be defined by the "asymmetric relationship" that exists between a performers *intent* and the response of the instrument. While the term *resistances* does still contain an implicit suggestion of control, these ideas are still useful and it is possible to consider this asymmetry as being related to non-linearity.

1.4 Strange Attractors

The non-linearities and chaotic behaviour of strange attractors seem particularly suited to this kind of material focused creative exploration, since they do not simply exhibit unpredictable behaviour, but a whole spectrum of dynamics from entirely structured and periodic, to chaotic and non-repeating.

The use of chaotic and non-linear systems in music practice certainly has precedent however. There is a rich strand of experimental musicians who not only embrace non-linear and unpredictable processes as part of their practice, but intentionally cede some control and agency to the instruments they create. Musicians working in the early 20th century such as John Cage, David Tudor, Alvin Lucier, Iannis Xenakis and many others began to be influenced by cybernetic principles [9]. Later on in the 20th century, there are artists working *explicitly* with chaotic models; Di Scipioi [10], Ikeshiro [11], Bayle [12], Mudd [2] among many others. For a good overview see [2].

The resources currently available to artists wanting to work with strange attractors in particular are limited. The Supercollider platform³ provides a range of chaotic oscillators and non-linear dynamical systems. In a similar way, for the Max platform, André Sier's A-Chaos Lib⁴ is a collection of strange attractors and non-linear dynamical systems, however the package is no longer maintained or compatible with the latest versions of Max. Both of these packages offer the attractors themselves but nothing more. There is no indication about how or why to use them in a musical way short of running them at audio rate as chaotic oscillators.

2. THE STRANGE PULSE TOOLKIT

The Strange Pulse Toolkit provides a set of tools to incorporate strange attractors into Max based digital instruments with an emphasis on rhythmical exploration and a material-oriented perspective on instrument design. While there is a rich vein of musical practice that has utilised complex systems of different kinds, there does not exist a toolkit that specifically considers strange attractors within the context of exploratory and experimental instrument design. The toolkit is unashamedly opinionated, and has a number of specific aims:

- Provide functionality for instrument design where some level of control is ceded to the dynamics of the attractor
- Enable a playful exploratory mode of instrument building by providing a range of utility modules and 'snippets'⁵ that allow a user to quickly patch together a functional instrument
- Provide mechanisms that allow 'Second Order' control: systems of analysis that can form feedback

³<https://supercollider.github.io/>

⁴<https://s373.net/code/A-Chaos-Lib/A-Chaos.html>

⁵<https://docs.cycling74.com/userguide/snippets/>

loops allowing the instrument to influence its own behaviour

2.1 Overview

The attractor is the central focal point for the toolkit. The performer/composer can play *with* the attractor, moving in and out of chaotic space, to influence the rhythmic characteristics. Parameters of the attractor can be modified directly to influence its behaviour. Additional strategies for influencing the attractors are given below in section 4.6.

Given the semi-structured, chaotic nature of the attractors, these signals can create complex and evolving patterns that are highly responsive to parameter changes and very suitable for rhythmical exploration.

2.1.1 An example flow

The Strange Pulse Toolkit is modular in design, and as such it can be utilised in any way deemed interesting or useful by the composer/performer. What follows is a description of a one approach to using the toolkit, drawn from my own experiences.

At its most basic, The Strange Pulse Toolkit's intended operational flow is very simple: The attractor outputs 3 signals, and each signal can be used to trigger MIDI events. In addition to this, the attractor signals can also be used as modulation sources, outputting MIDI CC messages or simply as Max signals.

Beyond this basic flow, there are some objects that can greatly increase the complexity of the system:

- Signals can be manipulated, combined and modified
- Triggers can be modified via arithmetic, algorithm or probability
- Feedback can be introduced into the system via audio analysis in the form of a multi-band envelope follower
- Complexity analysis capabilities are provided which enable the measurement of the complexity of the attractors

The toolkit is designed to be modular, allowing users to combine different components to create unique instruments and effects. The components of the toolkit include:

- **Attractors** - A number of attractors are provided as Max externals, written in C++ using Min-API⁶. These include Dadrás, Lorenz, Thomas, Chen-Lee, Hadley and Halvorsen. Additionally, a *gen~*⁷ patch is provided allowing users to easily add their own equations and implement their own attractors. Each of the provided attractors operates in 3D space and can run up into audio rate. The ability to synchronise two attractors is provided, which allows multiple attractors to run at different speeds but to be locked into the same trajectory. This can be useful since

⁶<https://github.com/Cycling74/min-devkit>

⁷https://docs.cycling74.com/userguide/gen/_gen_overview/

Figure 1. An example workflow using The Strange Pulse Toolkit.

a faster attractor very quickly exhibits its chaotic behaviour allowing for analysis with our complexity metrics listed below, whereas a slower attractor might make sense in terms of rhythm generation. Some simple visualisation patches are provided.

- **Signal Shapers** - A set of modular utilities allowing for the shaping of signals: attenuation, inversion, smoothing, scaling, wave-shaping and wave-folding.
- **Rhythm Makers** - Flexible signal to trigger generators using either explicit thresholds or using gradient change based triggering.
- **Rhythm Modifiers** - A suite of trigger modifiers: modulo, divide, multiply, repeater, quantise, probability and euclidean.
- **Destinations** - Simple MIDI note out objects, sequencer objects and envelope generators.
- **Feedback** - Objects enabling feedback in different ways. Audio based in the form of a multi-band envelope follower with additional threshold-based trigger outputs. Complexity metrics in the form of RPDE and RQA, described below.

3. COMPLEXITY METRICS

Following on from the work of Kiefer [?, ?] and Elia et al. [7], the use of complexity metrics affords a cybernetic loop, allowing an instrument to measure the complexity of the current attractor’s state. While Kiefer and Elia used Random Projection Complexity, and Higuchi Fractal Dimension respectively, recurrence-based approaches aligned more closely with the perceived complexity of the attractors. The toolkit provides one object for Recurrence Quantification Analysis which calculates the recurrence rate, determinism, laminarity, maximum diagonal line length, trapping time and entropy, as well as a related metric, the Recurrence Period Density Entropy (RPDE).

3.1 Recurrence Quantification Analysis

Recurrence Quantification Analysis (RQA) is a method of analysing dynamical systems based on the geometric characteristics of their recurrence plots. Recurrence plots were originally a visual tool for investigating the behaviour of dynamical systems [13, 14]. Webber and Zbilut [?, 15, 16] later developed analytical methods to quantify the characteristics of the recurrence data, rather than rely on visual analysis.

A recurrence plot can be defined like so:

$$R(i, j) = \Theta(\varepsilon - |0\vec{x}(i) - \vec{x}(j)|0) \quad (1)$$

where $\Theta : \mathbf{R} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ is a unit step function and ε is a threshold or tolerance value.

The most basic RQA measure is the **recurrence rate**:

$$RR = \frac{1}{N^2} \sum_{i,j=1}^N R(i, j) \quad (2)$$

which shows the density of recurrence points in the plot. Intuitively we can understand how this corresponds to the behaviour of a strange attractor being on a fixed periodic course rather than when it is on a chaotic path.

There are a range of other measures, which typically analyse the characteristics of lines, both vertical and diagonal found in the recurrence plot. Diagonal lines indicate segments of the trajectory which run parallel, whereas vertical lines represent segments of the trajectory that remain in the same area of phase space, or that move very slowly. Further details and mathematical formulation for the other measures can be found in [?, 15, 16].

A subset of the measures have been implemented for experimentation in The Strange Pulse Toolkit. They are:

- **Recurrence Rate** - defined above
- **Determinism** - the percentage of recurrence points that form diagonal lines
- **Laminarity** - the percentage of recurrence points that form vertical lines
- **Lmax** - the maximum length of of a diagonal line
- **Entropy** - the Shannon Entropy of the frequency distribution of diagonal line lengths
- **Trapping Time** - the average length of vertical lines

3.2 Recurrence Period Density Entropy

Recurrence period density entropy (RPDE) is a metric that also works with recurrence plots in an analytical way. Rather than a focus on geometric features as with RQA, RPDE focuses on the distribution of recurrence intervals. It computes the the probability density function of those intervals and then calculates the Shannon entropy, to give a single measure of complexity.

$$RPDE = -(\ln T_{\max})^{-1} \sum_{t=1}^{T_{\max}} P(t) \ln P(t) \quad (3)$$

Figure 2. RQA module analysing a stable trajectory of the Dadras Attractor. Outputting Recurrence Rate (black), Determinism (purple), Laminarity (green), Lmax (red), Entropy (orange), Trapping Time (blue)

Figure 3. RQA module analysing a chaotic trajectory of the Dadras Attractor. Outputting Recurrence Rate (black), Determinism (purple), Laminarity (green), Lmax (red), Entropy (orange), Trapping Time (blue)

where $P(t)$ is the probability density function, and T_{\max} is the largest recurrence value.

4. CASE STUDY: STRANGERAVE

StrangeRAVE is an instrument that I developed while exploring the themes and ideas around composing with strange attractors. Out of this instrument, came The Strange Pulse Toolkit. StrangeRAVE serves as a case study of using the toolkit, but also highlights the design processes that lead to the toolkit's development. An autobiographical approach to the design was taken [17]. While acknowledging the subjective stance this takes, it allows for fast, iterative design decisions to be made that aid in the development of my musical instrument. The toolkit emerged out of an abstraction of these design decisions.

Figure 4. A later iteration of StrangeRAVE incorporating most features from the Attractor Toolbox

4.1 Initial development

The initial development of StrangeRAVE began while experimenting with the 'percussion' RAVE⁸ model provided by IRCAM⁹. RAVE (Realtime Audio Variational autoEncoder) [18] is a real-time audio synthesis and transformation model. It uses a variational autoencoder architecture to encode audio into a low dimensional latent space. Novel audio can be generated by sampling from the latent space, although many uses for the RAVE model focus on its use as a style transfer tool^{10 11}.

While experimenting with the potential for using RAVE as a pure generative model, it was found that at certain speeds, traversing the latent space created novel percussive loops. Small changes in the trajectory made changes in the timbre and rhythm of the generated audio. I had an idea that using a strange attractor to traverse the latent space might allow interesting structural variation in the generated audio. Since the attractor can be periodic or chaotic, this could allow a controllable variation in drum loops.

The latent space in a RAVE model is typically between 4 and 16 dimensions, whereas the output of the strange attractor is only 3. In order to map from the latent space features onto the attractors position vectors a multi-layered perceptron (MLP) was trained using the Flucoma Toolkit¹², a technique recently used by Elia et al [7]. A number of points from the RAVE latent space were saved, along with the same number of points in the attractor 3D space. An MLP is then trained to learn a non-linear mapping between the lower dimensional attractor points and the higher dimensional RAVE latent space points.

Crucially, the non-linear mapping is useful not for the ability to recall the points learned during training, but for the ability to interpolate *between* points in a way that explores the latent space in an exploratory and sometimes unexpected way. Through trial and error I was able to discover trajectories that resulted in compelling loops, and initial attempts to modify the attractor signals began at this

⁸ <https://github.com/acids-ircam/RAVE>

⁹ https://acids-ircam.github.io/rave_models_download

¹⁰ <https://neutone.ai/fx>

¹¹ <https://forum.ircam.fr/projects/detail/rave-vst/>

¹² <https://learn.flucoma.org/learn/regression-neural-network/>

point(see figure 5). The ability to attenuate, scale, invert and smooth the signals could lead to interesting variations in the generated audio.

Figure 5. An early module for signal attenuation, inversion, scaling, and smoothing

4.2 Percussive development

Since the initial success lead in a percussive direction, I continued to think of ways that the attractor could be lent towards rhythmical generation.

Using the position values of the attractor and a threshold value, allowed me to trigger samples. Each threshold could trigger two samples, depending on the direction that the threshold was crossed. Given that each of the signals was bipolar, having two threshold values made sense. This meant that a total of 12 separate samples could be triggered from the 3 signals.

Figure 6. A module to generate 4 MIDI events from a 1D signal

This design was later refined to be based not on threshold values, but on a change in gradient sign. This way, any change in the relative amplitude of the signals would not require adjusting the threshold values.

Even with this very limited set of functionality, some musically interesting results could be found and I spent some time exploring the potential for this experimental instrument.

The ability modify the trigger signals was an obvious area to explore. Adding some simple arithmetic conditions such as modulo and probability immediately added a lot of diversity and flexibility to the instrument.

Figure 7. Part of the modulation and preset capabilities from StrangeRAVE

4.3 Modulation Flexibility

StrangeRAVE makes extensive use of modulation matrices to maximize the use of attractor signals as modulators. These matrices allow the attractor signals to be routed to various destinations across the instrument. The matrices can be randomised and their state saved as presets, which can then be interpolated. See figure 7.

4.4 Audio Feedback

The first feedback mechanism introduced was a band limited envelope follower with a threshold based trigger. The output of the whole system was fed back into this envelope follower and certain frequency bands isolated. The resulting signal could be used for modulation purposes, and in addition a trigger output could be generated based on a threshold. This trigger could be routed to any of the existing destination modules; a midi note, a midi sequencer or an envelope.

4.5 Effects and Master Chain

The instrument includes an effects section that features reverb, delay, and spectral processing units. These effects are arranged in a 'send' configuration, allowing for flexible routing and blending of the processed signals. Each effect can be modulated using a modulation matrix, providing dynamic control over the effect parameters.

Finally, there is a master effects chain that processes the final output of the instrument. This chain includes a multi-band expander to enhance the dynamic range and a limiter to prevent clipping and ensure a consistent output level.

Figure 8. A band limited envelope follower, with various trigger options

4.6 User Control

There are a range of ways that the user can interact with the instrument. The parameters of the chosen attractor can be manually modified with sliders.

Figure 9. Manual control of the attractor. Also showing some of the visualisation options

In order to see the effect of the change in parameters, several ways to view the attractor are given. A 3D visualisation that can be rotated, panned, and zoomed with the mouse is provided. Additionally, a second attractor running in sync with the first but at much higher speed is shown as three 1D plots as shown in figure 9. This representation allows a much faster way to visually evaluate the chaotic behaviour of the attractor.

In addition to manual adjustment - the preset system of Max can be used to not only store parameter states, but to linearly interpolate between them. This allows for easy navigation between known states.

Finally an MLP can be used as already mentioned in section 4.1 to learn a non-linear mapping between 2D points in an XY display and the parameters of the chosen attractor.

4.7 Second Order Feedback Control

In order to achieve the aim of ceding control back to the instrument, additional levels of self-reflection were needed. I took inspiration from Kiefer's approach to real time complexity analysis [19] and Elia et al. [7] and their implementation of a drunken walk around the parametric space of their no-input mixer. The audio output of their instrument was analysed by the Higuchi Fractal Dimension metric [20] which was inversely mapped to the speed of the walk so that more complex regions were explored more slowly, and less complex areas were moved over quickly.

I considered a similar approach in StrangeRAVE, I could allow the instrument to find areas of complexity 'by itself' rather than navigating manually. I evaluated the metrics present in Kiefer's libccrt¹³ library as a starting point. Both Kiefer and Elia were analysing audio rate data, where as my attractor was running at a much slower speed. In order to fairly evaluate them I ran my attractors at audio rate, alongside an attractor running at normal speed - both were synchronised to ensure the same trajectory was evaluated. While some correspondence was found with the metrics tested (Higuchi, Sevcik [21], and Random Projection Complexity [22]) and the apparent complexity of the attractor, I began to evaluate other approaches.

¹³ <https://github.com/chriskiefer/libccrt>

I found that the recurrence based approaches, specifically RQA and RPDE (as mentioned in sections: 3.1 and 3.2) although highly sensitive to the chosen parameters, were much more effective at reflecting the chaotic nature of the attractors.

With this functionality I implemented "Search for Periodicity" and "Search for Chaos" options that would use the output of the RPDE measure and that would guide the amount of noise added to the attractor parameters. Although the RQA measures are not currently used in StrangeRAVE, the additional detail it provides could allow for more nuanced control.

4.8 Summary

The Strange Pulse Toolkit emerged from the development of the StrangeRAVE instrument. While StrangeRAVE is a highly personalized instrument with unique features that may not appeal to a huge audience of musicians, the underlying concepts and approach have broader relevance. The toolkit implemented in this instrument encouraged me to embrace both the unpredictability and the inherent structure of strange attractors, fostering a more exploratory creation process where direct control and mastery of the instrument are no longer guiding principles.

Some sample music created with strangeRAVE can be found online¹⁴.

5. REFLECTIONS/FUTURE WORK

The Strange Pulse Toolkit presented here is a novel contribution and provides new resources for artists engaged with experimental and material-oriented instrument design. It aims to encourage a ceding of control from the musician and sees co-creation as its primary creative paradigm. It does this by providing not just the attractors themselves, but a range of utilities, modules and examples that encourage and illustrate this kind of use. Additionally, all the supplementary functionality allows users to remain in a playful exploratory mode of instrument building since common utilities and functionality is ready to use. The inclusion of complexity metrics enables instruments built with this toolkit to self-reflect - to feedback into themselves and to implement self-regulatory behaviours.

While an autobiographical approach to creating my instruments and subsequently the toolkit has been a very fruitful method, further development could involve user-centred studies in the form of workshops or longer-term engagement. The autobiographical approach is knowingly biased, providing insights that work very well for my personal artistic development. Engaging with a user-focused study could lead the development of the toolkit in directions that are more broadly applicable to a wider audience of musicians.

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